

Impact of Frame Type on the Sensitivity of Ice Load Measurements Systems

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Abstract. Safe and efficient structural design requires knowledge of loading conditions. The importance of understanding the magnitude of the local ice-induced load on the ship structure is acknowledged due to the increasing maritime activities in waters with seasonal or year-round ice coverage. The stochastic nature of the ship-ice interaction process has emphasized the importance of full-scale measurements. The local ice loads are commonly determined by measuring hull response and utilizing inverse engineering to define load from the response. Shear strain difference-based measurements combined with the Influence Coefficient Matrix (ICM) to define strain-load relation are state-of-the-art techniques for indirect ice load measurements. However, this technique has shown limitations that can affect the measurement accuracy. To improve the understanding of the uncertainty related to the method, this paper studies the impact of structural details on the uncertainty of transversely-framed ships. At first, this paper defines the sufficient extent of the numerical model for the construction of ICM using FE analysis. The study shows that the extended model is less sensitive to the selection of boundary conditions. Then, the model is applied to investigate the outcome by changing the frame cross-sectional profile from the flat bar to bulb flat. It is observed that the asymmetric profile can introduce additional uncertainties, especially under the single-sided instrumentation. Finally, a discrepancy found from the previous research and an uncertainty reduction method are discussed. As the study focuses on the response of the structure within the linear elastic domain, the first-year ice class design criteria defined by the Finnish and Swedish Ice Class Rule (FSICR), the approach of decomposing the larger load patch to smaller ones becomes possible and serves as the foundation of minimizing the computational burden and the uncertainty reduction method.

Key words: Ice load, Inverse method, Boundary condition, Transverse frame, Uncertainty, Numerical simulation

1. Introduction

Sea ice imposes challenges to the design and operation of the ship. Besides the global ship-ice interaction problem that affects the performance, such as the resistance and maneuvering, the ice load acting on the ship structure can be highly localized, which demands an additional structural strengthening compared to the open water design. The problem of the localized ice load has attracted special attention from the Baltic countries, especially Finland, because of the first-year ice developed annually in the Baltic Sea, and more than 80% of imports and exports are transported through sea [1]. To ensure the safety of marine transportation in ice, the Finnish-Swedish Ice Class Rule (FSICR) [2] specifies minimum structural scantling based on elastic design limit, which assumes a limit that the shell plating or supporting structures reach yield at least once per winter [3]. The idealization of the elastic design limit marks the key distinction in contrast to the IACS [4] polar rule, which optimizes the design efficiency in more severe multi-year ice conditions observed in the polar regions, using the plastic design limit.

The FSICR continuously evolves as the understanding of the ship-ice interaction process improves. The process is considered stochastic with significant uncertainties that are difficult to analyze. The load height, which is the vertical extent of an ice load event, defined in the level ice contact scenario was initially taken as the entire ice thickness, with the corrections applied considering the hull angle. The model was later revisited, leading to reductions of the load height. This results in a more concentrated design line load acting

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on a smaller area, which causes a higher stress as the load magnitude remains the same [3][5]. The change is based on the observations obtained from the full-scale measurement and the improved understanding of the ice failure and the structure-ice interaction theories, which also depend on the validation from the full-scale result. As a result, the reliability of the full-scale measurement system becomes a critical problem that must be secured.

Suominen [6] summarizes that the full-scale ice load measurement system can be divided into two categories: direct and indirect systems. As the direct ice load measurement system is subjected to significant wear and tear or modifications to the structural stiffness, indirect measurements through strain gauges have gained popularity in previous research. Although the theory behind the method is straightforward with a relatively simple measurement configuration, measuring errors due to noise, errors due to inadequate or inexact modeling quality, and numerical errors behind the theory can all contribute to the deviation of the obtained ice load compared to reality. Applying round-off through safety factors can provide sufficient design safety if the ice load is obtained to the correct order of magnitude. Still, an effort to understand and reduce the errors is essential for achieving an efficient structure design, and contributes to the improvement of the existing ice rules.

Therefore, an uncertainty analysis of the ice load measurement method is conducted in this study through FE analysis, and one of the focuses of the study is to understand how asymmetric frame profiles can affect the existing Influence Coefficient Matrix (ICM) method on the transversely framed ship structures, a topic that has not been previously investigated. The scope of the analysis is limited to the linear elastic domain as per FSICR. The methodology behind ICM and the previous uncertainty analysis are first discussed in Section 2., with the introduction to the numerical model used in the analysis. Section 3. compares the differences in the inverted ice load magnitude obtained from the trimmed and extended grillage model. Then, an analysis of the frame type is presented in Section 4.. Based on the observations, a methodology is proposed in Section 5.2. to reduce the numerical errors from the inverted results.

2. Methodology

2.1. Influence coefficient matrix

Deriving the local ice load from the strain gauges attached to the structure is considered an inverse problem. For a transversely framed ship, a common configuration of the measurement system is to attach pairs of shear strain gauges to frames within the interested measurement region. For each shear strain gauge pair, one is attached to the lower end and the other is attached to the upper end of the frame. In this paper, the definition of the lower and upper ends of a frame is related to the local -y and +y direction as shown in 3.b. The difference between the lower and upper shear strain readings is proportional to the magnitude of the load acting on the frames, according to the classic beam theory shown in Figure 3.a. The inverted load acting on a frame can be presented as

$$f_n = a_n(\delta\gamma_n), \quad (1)$$

where a_n is the stiffness parameter that relates the applied load and the measured strain difference, and n is the index number of the frame. The summation of the f_n on adjacent frames with the gauge pairs attached provides the inverted total ice load acting within the instrumentation region. A FE model is applied to obtain the stiffness parameter a_n by solving for the lower and upper shear strain from a unit load acting at the midspan of the frame. Physical calibration can be conducted afterward to check for agreement, and an example can be found in [7]. Previous studies show that the inverse method can provide consistent results although the spatial distribution of the shear strain is not constant over the frame surface, as long as the load is applied between a gauge pair and a sufficient distance margin is provided in between.

Since the frames are analyzed individually, the effect of load transfer is not included in the aforementioned method. An improved inverse method, namely ICM, was proposed to capture the load transfer behavior within the grillage structure when inverting the applied ice load. Suominen et al. [8] show that the load gets redistributed to adjacent frames depending on the ratio between the plate stiffness and the frame bending and rotational stiffness. For a small load patch that can be treated as a point force acting perpendicular to a central frame, at least two adjacent frames on each side of the central one should be taken

into account [8]. Equation 2 is modified into matrix form to include the load transfer mechanism within the grillage system:

$$[F] = [A][\Delta\gamma]. \quad (2)$$

Defining a new parameter C that is the inverse of A , Equation 3 can be rewritten and expanded as

$$\begin{bmatrix} c_{1,1} & c_{1,2} & \dots & c_{1,n} \\ c_{2,1} & c_{2,2} & \dots & c_{2,n} \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ c_{n,1} & c_{n,2} & \dots & c_{n,n} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} f_1 \\ f_2 \\ \dots \\ f_n \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} \delta\gamma_1 \\ \delta\gamma_2 \\ \dots \\ \delta\gamma_n \end{Bmatrix}. \quad (3)$$

The matrix C is obtained similarly as the inverse of a_n from Equation 1. Except this time shear strain differences are retrieved from the number of n instrumented frames and entered into the corresponding row of C . The same procedure is repeated until all the rows are filled. Then Equation 2 is applied to invert the ice load from the full-scale strain measurement. The summation of all the entries within the vector F returns the total ice load applied to the instrumentation area.

Instead of installing a pair of shear strain gauges on one side of the frames, double-sided instrumentation installs one pair on each side of the frame. The advantage of the double-sided instrumentation is the ability to average the shear strain difference due to the frame rotation, in which case a significant difference can be found in the shear strain reading between the opposite faces [8]. Böhm et al. [10] further confirm the improvement of the measurement accuracy through FE analysis. Note that this observation is obtained based on the analyses of the flat bar. Studies of asymmetrical frame profiles are conducted in Section 4.1..

Regardless of the methods and the instrumentation configurations to be taken, discrepancies exist between the inverted load magnitude compared to the actual load acting on the structure. This difference is defined as the load magnitude uncertainty to be investigated in later sections.

2.2. Model

A transversely framed grillage model is created for the study. The geometry and dimensions of the model are modified from MT Uikku [11]. The FE model is illustrated in Figure 1. and 2. with dimensions and material parameters listed in Table 1.. The grillage is modeled with one of the frame profiles provided in the table, and the comparison is made between the calculations obtained from the two frame profiles. The bulb flat dimensions in Table 1. originate from dimensions of the industrial standard 340*14 bulb, using the translation equations from the structural design principles chapter provided by DNV [12]. The second area moment I and polar moment J are kept similar for the two frame profiles to ensure both the bending and rotational stiffness are comparable. The post-yield properties are not considered as the study is limited to the elastic domain.

Abaqus is applied for the FE analysis. The grillage model is divided into two regions: the trimmed region and the extended region. The trimmed region is constructed of 40*40 mm quadrilateral mesh elements, while the mesh size in the extended region transitions from 40*40 mm to about 100 mm. Shell elements are used with a total number of 43,000. The boundary of the trimmed region is at the intersection with the webframes and stringers, see Figure 2.. The coarser mesh sizes beyond the trimmed region are considered acceptable, because in this study the load is applied to the plating of the trimmed region. The ordered squared mesh elements on the plating simplify the automation of the FE analysis and enable the application of the superposition method when constructing a larger load patch from smaller ones. The method is discussed in detail under Section 2.3.. The model with only the trimmed region is analyzed independently from the other part in Section 3. when investigating the effect of the boundary condition. In this case, the webframes and stringers are removed from the trimmed model with either fixed or simple support applied directly to the edges.

Figure 1. The grillage geometry and corresponding mesh elements. The two frame profiles used in the study are illustrated within the circle.

Figure 2. The trimmed region is circled by a dashed square. A smooth transition zone is provided between the extended region and the trimmed region.

Table 1. *Dimensions, section properties, and material properties of the model*

	l [mm]	s [mm]	hw [mm]	tw [mm]	bf [mm]	tf [mm]
Webframes	3*3000	2800	800	22	140	24
Stringers	3*2800	3000	660	18	140	20
Frame	Flat bar	3000	400	430	N/A	N/A
	340*14 Bulb	3000	400	340	63	35
	tp [mm]	23.5			ν	0.3
	E [GPa]	206			σ_y [MPa]	235

*l - span. s - spacing. hw - web height. tw - web thickness. bf - flange width.
tp - plate thickness. ν - Poisson's ratio. E - Elastic Modules. σ_y - yield strength.

Figure 3. (a) Shear strain distribution from classic beam theory and (b) shear strain distribution from FE analysis. The 10 shear strain measurement locations are labeled on the figure.

”3Co principle” proposed by Song et al. [13] is followed when creating the FE model for the bulb flat. The method acknowledges the importance of correspondence, comparability, and competence when modeling the bulb flat for the FE analysis. The study [13] shows that the shell-only model provides adequate quality under the linear analysis. Hence, the shell-only model is applied as it reduces the modeling and computational effort.

To further support the boundary condition and gauge location study covered in Section 3., the response of the grillage model is measured in terms of shear strains at 10 locations (5 gauge pairs) on each frame within the trimmed region, see Figure 3.b. The shear strains are measured close to the neutral axis of the frame as per the recommendation provided by Böhm et al. [10]. One element spacing (40 mm) is maintained between adjacent pairs on both ends along the local y-axis.

2.3. Superposition method

A large ice-induced load patch can be decomposed into smaller load patches [8]. This understanding implies that the response of the structure caused by a larger load patch is equivalent to the sum of the unit responses. This is valid as long as the structure is loaded within the linear-elastic assumption. Figure 4. illustrates the method. Consider a scenario where a rectangular load patch is applied to the center of the model. The response of each frame within the instrumentation area to the load is measured in terms of $\delta\gamma_n^{total}$, which is the difference between the shear strain measured at the lower and upper ends of a frame. Multiplying $\delta\gamma_n^{total}$ with the stiffness term a_n or the matrix A gives F_{total} , the inverted total ice load. Alternatively, the unit response $\delta\gamma_n^{i,j}$ due to each unit load patch, that is a part of the larger load patch, can be simply summed together to provide the same results as treating the load patch as a whole. The mathematical description is

$$\delta\gamma_n^{total} = \sum \delta\gamma_n^{i,j}. \quad (4)$$

Figure 4. Decomposition of a larger load patch into unit patches.

This method eliminates the need to repeat the FE analysis when checking the load magnitude uncertainty of any load patches, after responses due to all unit load patches are calculated. The unit responses can be scaled up or down linearly according to the magnitude and distribution of the combined load patch. The principle of superposition also serves as a foundation of the uncertainty reduction method proposed in Section 5.2..

3. Effect of gauge locations and boundary conditions

The goal of this section is to understand how the gauge locations and boundary conditions affect the load magnitude uncertainty. First, ICMs (or A) are derived from the center grillage (the trimmed region) of 1) the model with only the trimmed region and 2) the model with the extended region, by applying double-sided instrumentation on the flat bar profile. Both fixed and simply supported boundaries are considered. The magnitude of the calibration load is 1 kN.

A comparison is made among the ICMs derived from the trimmed model and extended model, with either a fixed or simply-supported boundary. All the ICMs under the comparison are derived from the third gauge pair shown in Figure 3.b. The method to derive the ICMs follows the discussion provided in Section 2.1., by applying a unit point load of 1 kN perpendicularly to an individual mesh element. The area subject to the load is small from the perspective of the entire model and can therefore be considered as a point. The load pushes to the plating location that is directly on top of the midspan of each frame within the trimmed region, one by one, until all the entries are filled. For the equations presented below, the first superscript letter describes whether the ICMs are obtained from the extended (e) or trimmed (t) model, and the second letter indicates fixed (f) or simple (s) boundary conditions. Equation 5 shows that the ICMs derived from the extended model are the same up to the second decimal place, regardless of the defined boundary conditions. However, significant differences are observed from the trimmed model under the two boundary conditions, as shown in Equation 6 and 7. The comparison implicitly suggests that the effect of the boundary conditions on the load magnitude uncertainty becomes negligible if a sufficiently large computational domain is included in the FE model.

$$[A]_3^{es} \approx [A]_3^{ef} = \begin{bmatrix} 589.54 & -158.62 & 11.08 & -5.25 & 1.04 & -0.90 \\ -171.66 & 581.29 & -153.05 & 16.93 & -1.48 & -0.47 \\ 19.95 & -155.12 & 577.43 & -154.25 & 15.82 & -2.45 \\ -2.45 & 15.82 & -154.25 & 577.43 & -155.12 & 19.95 \\ -0.47 & -1.48 & 16.93 & -153.05 & 581.29 & -171.66 \\ -0.9 & 1.04 & -5.25 & 11.08 & -158.62 & 589.54 \end{bmatrix} MN \quad (5)$$

$$[A]_3^{tf} = \begin{bmatrix} 538.16 & -108.51 & -7.38 & 6.62 & -1.52 & 0.03 \\ -111.11 & 494.4 & -87.33 & -9.45 & 6.21 & -1.37 \\ -6.57 & -87.99 & 488.99 & -87.86 & -9.26 & 6.44 \\ 6.44 & -9.26 & -87.86 & 488.99 & -87.99 & -6.57 \\ -1.37 & 6.21 & -9.45 & -87.33 & 494.4 & -111.11 \\ 0.03 & -1.52 & 6.62 & -7.38 & -108.51 & 538.16 \end{bmatrix} MN \quad (6)$$

$$[A]_3^{ts} = \begin{bmatrix} 446.65 & -83.93 & -8.59 & 5.84 & -1.1 & -0.02 \\ -83.95 & 487.7 & -87.18 & -9.51 & 6.18 & -1.08 \\ -8.5 & -87.21 & 488.8 & -87.32 & -9.47 & 5.84 \\ 5.84 & -9.47 & -87.32 & 488.8 & -87.21 & -8.5 \\ -1.08 & 6.18 & -9.51 & -87.18 & 487.7 & -83.95 \\ -0.02 & -1.1 & 5.84 & -8.59 & -83.93 & 446.65 \end{bmatrix} MN \quad (7)$$

Next, derived ICMs are applied to obtain the inverted load from $\delta\gamma_n$, which is caused by a unit point load applied to each mesh element of the plate within the trimmed region, in the local $z(+)$ direction. The magnitude of the unit load is the same as the calibration load. The extended region is kept in this calculation because the extended model provides a more accurate representation of the actual ship structure under the

ice load. The relative error between the inverted and applied loads is mapped for the entire trimmed region, as the example shown in Figure 5..

It is observed from Figure 5. that as the gauge pair locations move from inward to outward, the effective measurement area within the trimmed region, where the relative error to the true unit load (1 kN) is less than 50%, increases. The region shaded in dark blue is considered ineffective with large errors. This distribution pattern aligns with the earlier observation by Böhm [10]. The distributions of the relative error along the local x-axis are provided in Figure 6., along 10, 15, 25, and 38 element rows counted from the upper end of the trimmed region. Besides Row 10, where the applied unit load is close to the gauge locations, the distributions at the center part are not sensitive to the position of the gauge pairs, which are positioned along the neutral axis of the frame.

Based on the understanding above, another comparison is made among the results obtained from the extended model with fixed boundary, the trimmed model with fixed boundary, and the trimmed model with simple boundary, see Figure 7.. Along the first and sixth frames, the unit load tends to be overestimated, as already been shown by Böhm [10]. The overestimation along those two frames is most significant for the results calculated from the fixed boundary conditions, and the magnitude is identical between the extended and the trimmed model. In the center, the same pattern is found in the three models, but the trimmed model provides an overall better estimation closer to the true unit load. The mean and standard deviation obtained from the three models are listed in Table 2., within the effective measurement area.

It is found that shifting the gauge pairs outward to a reasonable extent can increase the effective measurement area without compromising the results. Also, there is insufficient evidence to show that the extended model can provide a more accurate load inversion compared to the trimmed model. However, it is clear that the extended model is much less sensitive to the selected boundary conditions. Additional investigations might be needed when dealing with more complicated grillage geometries.

Figure 5. From left to right: relative errors of unit loads inverted from the gauge pair 5, gauge pair 3, and gauge pair 1. The horizontal and vertical axes indicate the mesh element counts along the local x and y-axis

Figure 6. The distribution of the inverted unit load concerning the three gauge pairs, at four rows. The horizontal axis indicates the mesh element counts along the local x-axis. The magnitude of the inverted load and true unit load is given on the vertical axis in kN.

Figure 7. The distribution of the inverted unit load concerning the three models, at four rows. The horizontal axis indicates the mesh element counts along the local x-axis. The magnitude of the inverted load and true unit load is given on the vertical axis in kN.

Table 2. Means and standard deviation of the extended model with fixed boundary, the trimmed model with fixed boundary, and the trimmed model with simple boundary inside the effective measurement area

Model	$\mu_{relative\ error}, \%$	$\sigma_{relative\ error}, \%$
Extended + fixed	-0.06	7.52
Trimmed + fixed	1.91	6.36
Trimmed + simple	-0.64	4.36

4. Effect of frame type

4.1. Asymmetric frame profile

The bulb flat frame profile is commonly seen in many ships operating in first-year ice conditions. Unlike the flat or Tee bar, its asymmetrical profile can amplify uncertainties in the ice load measurement using the inverse methods. The issues can be viewed from two perspectives: From the global scale of the grillage structure, the implementation of the asymmetric frame profile can break the symmetry of the structure, if the structure under consideration is simple like the example provided in this study. From the local scale of the frame itself, the frame can experience rotation even though a unit load directly applies to the frame. Previous research has shown that frame rotation can lead to different shear strain measurements on the two opposite faces [8]. The extended model is used for the following analysis since it provides a more accurate representation of the actual structure and is insensitive to the selection of the boundary conditions. The load is inverted based on the measurements from the third gauge pair as illustrated by Figure 3.b.

From the global perspective, one of the critical questions that should be addressed is whether the double-sided instrumentation can still provide better results compared to the single-sided instrumentation, when the frame profile is asymmetric. Figure 8. compares the distributions of the relative errors among the two single-sided instrumentation (top and bottom faces) and the double-sided instrumentation. The method of obtaining the distributions from ICMs is similar to the method discussed in Section 3.. Except for the top and bottom-sided instrumentation, ICMs and the resultant shear strain difference $\delta\gamma_n$ due to a unit point load are obtained based on the gauge measurements on a single face instead of taking the average between the two faces. The top face is the one with the flange extrusion, while the bottom face is flat. Although the distributions obtained from the single-sided instrumentation are no longer mirrored about the grillage center, which is the case for the symmetric frame profile, the double-sided instrumentation retains a mirrored distribution pattern similar to the results obtained from the symmetric frame profile. From

the comparison provided in Table 3., it is noticed that the bottom-sided instrumentation provides a more accurate load inversion compared to the top-sided instrumentation and the double-sided instrumentation, except at the center part where the relative error of the double-sided instrumentation reaches the minimum. The double-sided instrumentation always provides the least standard deviation along the given rows, since the distribution pattern is symmetric and follows sinusoidal shapes. Although full-scale studies have shown it is common for the ice-induced load length, which is the horizontal extent of an ice load event, to extend for multiple frames [9], the possibility of encountering a narrow load exists, which differs from the means that are obtained through the entire length of 2.8 m at the six rows given in the table. This implies that the double-sided instrumentation might still be preferable as it is more likely for the (+) and (-) errors to be canceled out.

Figure 8. From left to right: relative errors of unit loads inverted from top, double, and bottom-sided instrumentation. The horizontal and vertical axes indicate the mesh element counts along the local x and y-axis.

Figure 9. The distribution of the inverted unit load concerning the three instrumentation configurations, at four rows. The horizontal axis indicates the mesh element counts along the local x-axis. The magnitude of the inverted load and true unit load is given on the vertical axis in kN.

Table 3. Means and standard deviation of the bulb flat frame with top, bottom, and double-sided instrumentation inside the effective measurement area.

Model	$\mu_{relative\ error}, \%$						
	Row 10	Row 15	Row 20	Row 25	Row 30	Row 38	
Top-sided	8.52	7.59	5.33	3.07	1.51	0.56	
Double-sided	6.02	3.98	2.48	1.25	0.55	0.25	
Bottom-sided	3.33	-0.06	-0.36	0.05	0.61	1.06	
Model	$\sigma_{relative\ error}, \%$						
	Top-sided	13.78	11.47	9.10	7.43	6.29	5.68
	Double-sided	11.85	9.88	8.04	6.80	6.02	5.56
	Bottom-sided	13.03	10.40	8.34	7.14	6.44	6.07

The local scale problem is relevant to an existing calibration practice, which is to apply a method called the "calibration pull" to validate the ICMs obtained from the FE analyses. Detailed discussions on the topic can be found in the previous research conducted by Suominen et al. [7]. In brief, the ICM is obtained by pulling the midspans of frames one by one with a winch, so the shear strain at the gauge locations can be measured under a selected calibration load. The procedure is similar to the numerical method that has been discussed. Due to the setup of aligning the pulling cable with the shear center of the frame, and the moment to resist rotation when the pulling location is near the flange end of the frame, the frame tends to deflect without rotation. However, this frame deflection behavior introduced in the calibration pull is different from the behavior in the real loading scenario, where the ice load applies to the structure through pushing on the shell plating. By decomposing the longer load patch into unit patches, the unit load that is normal to the frame will introduce a rotation during the deflection, due to the asymmetric frame profile. This difference in structural responses may contribute to additional load magnitude uncertainties.

The relative differences between the loads inverted from the pushing and pulling ICMs are shown in Figure 10., with the definition of the relative difference provided in Equation 8. The pushing ICMs are obtained similarly as earlier discussion in Section 3., while the pulling ICMs are obtained by shifting the calibration load from the plating, or the frame root, to the tip that is near the flange. The difference is small for the double-sided instrumentation, but the inverted load tends to be larger for the top-sided instrumentation if the ICM is derived from pulling instead of pushing, and the situation is reversed for the bottom-sided instrumentation. Also comparing with the results in Figure 9., in which case the ICM is obtained from pushing, the ICM derived from pulling can lead to larger load magnitude uncertainties for both the top and bottom-sided instrumentation.

Figure 10. The relative difference between the inverted loads derived from pushing and pulling ICMs, under the three instrumentation configurations, at four rows. The horizontal axis indicates the mesh element counts along the local x-axis. The vertical axis shows the relative difference in percentage.

$$\delta_{ij}\% = \frac{f_{ij}^{pull} - f_{ij}^{push}}{f_{ij}^{push}} \cdot 100\% \quad (8)$$

4.2. Cutout

Frame cutouts can affect the distribution of the shear strain locally. Within the linear-elastic analysis, the shear strain will follow a linear response as the load increases, so it is speculated that the load measurement uncertainty will not be compromised by the feature. Further analysis of this topic is not included in this study, as an extensive amount of work is needed to accurately model the cutout inside the grillage system. Instead, this section investigates the uncertainty related to the determination of the vertical load location.

Böhm et al. proposed that the vertical location of the load center can be determined from the ratio of the upper and lower shear strain measurements as

$$\zeta = \frac{\gamma_{upper} L}{\gamma_{upper} - \gamma_{lower}}, \quad (9)$$

where γ_{upper} and γ_{lower} are shear strains measured at each end of a frame, and L is the frame span. The positions of the upper and lower gauges are symmetric about the midspan of the frame.

Figure 11. shows a FE model of a flat bar with a cutout at one end. The cutout has a radius of 4 cm. The flat bar shares the same dimensions as ones provided in Table 1., and it is attached to a one-frame spacing (400 mm) plating with fixed boundary conditions at both ends. A point load with a magnitude of 1 kN is applied to the midspan. The distributions of the shear strain within the shaded area with and without the cutout are presented in Figure 12.. It is found that the influence of the cutout on the problem diminishes as the gauge location moves further away from the cutout, especially along the local z-direction. As the resultant variation to the load location estimation is less than 5%, it is concluded that the presence of the cutout does not significantly alter the estimation results as long as a reasonable distance margin is provided in between.

Figure 11. The geometry of the frame with cutout. Only the cutout end of the frame is shown. The region subjected to the shear strain distribution study is shaded in red.

Figure 12. (a) The shear strain distribution at the cutout end, (b) the shear strain distribution at the intact end, and (c) the estimated load location in percentage of the total span.

5. Reduction of load magnitude uncertainties

5.1. Observed discrepancy

Before continuing the discussion of the correction method using the superposition principle, a discrepancy observed between the current and previous studies is presented.

Besides the load magnitude uncertainty of the unit point load applied to the grillage structure, Böhm et al. in 2021 [10] also investigate the load magnitude uncertainty related to larger load patches. The grillage model and method used by Böhm et al. are similar to this study, with the biggest exceptions in dimensions, frame numbers (five instead of six), and the model is trimmed to only include the plating and five frames attached to it. Three uniform load patches with lengths of half-frame spacing (0.2 m), one-frame spacing (0.4 m), and two-frame spacing (0.8 m) are covered in the study. The load height is 0.3 m, which is considered a reasonable assumption for the line-like load induced by the first-year level ice. From the results provided in the paper, large relative errors with magnitudes up to more than 50% (note that the original paper uses the absolute error as the indicator) are observed in the vicinity of the central frame, as the load length increases from the half-frame to the two-frame spacing. The horizontal extent of this high load magnitude uncertainty area is about one-frame spacing, extending vertically through the entire model. Referring to the original paper for more details.

To understand the reason behind this high load magnitude uncertainty at the center, the experiment is repeated in this study using the model discussed in Section 2.2. with the flat bar profile. The double-sided instrumentation is applied with shear strains obtained from the third gauge pair. Three uniform load patches share the same load lengths as the ones used by Böhm et al.. The load height of 0.28 m is used instead, since the squared mesh elements within the trimmed region are 40*40 mm. The difference should be negligible. The load magnitude uncertainty of the load patches centered at each element within the trimmed region is then checked using the superposition principle discussed in Section 2.3.: As the applied load is uniform across the load patches, the decomposed unit loads acting on each mesh element must be the same, so the resultant relative errors of the load patches is simply the average of all the relative errors due to the decomposed unit loads. Since the computation has already been completed for each mesh element as shown in Figure 5.b, FE analysis is no longer needed for the following calculations.

Figure 13. shows the relative errors between the inverted load and the true applied load, for the three load patches centered at each element within the computation region. The presented mappings are from the extended model, but the results retrieved from the trimmed model provide a similar pattern. The relative error distribution pattern of the half-frame spacing load patch is similar to the observation from Böhm et al.. One of the most relevant features is the areas of overestimation distributed along the first and sixth frames, and the magnitude of the overestimation reduces as the load length increases. When the load length increases, however, the high load magnitude uncertainty at the center is never observed as anticipated. The relative errors at the center are between 0 to -5%, and the distribution is getting smoother as the load length increases.

This observation contradicts the claim that the accuracy is negatively correlated with the load length when applying the ICM method [10].

Figure 13. The relative errors of the load magnitude obtained from the three load patches. The cross marks within the red boxes indicate the load center of the outermost load patches, which define the boundaries of the calculation domains. The horizontal and vertical axes indicate the mesh element counts along the local x and y-axis.

5.2. Uncertainty reduction

From the load magnitude uncertainty analysis provided in Section 3. and 4., it is confirmed again that the ICM method can invert ice load magnitude up to an acceptable level, which is about $\pm 20\%$ compared to the true unit load within the effect measurement area. If a longer load is applied along the midspan of the frames, the load magnitude uncertainty is small. Alternatively, a shorter load that is centered near the horizontal or vertical boundary of the effective measurement area is subject to the largest uncertainty. The level of accuracy is sufficient for conservative designs, but it is desirable to improve the measurement accuracy further from the perspective of efficient structure design. Hence, an uncertainty reduction method is proposed in this section based on the superposition principle.

5.2.1. Introduction to the method

The basic idea of the method is that if the vertical and horizontal positions of the load center, load length, and load height of a load patch can be estimated, then corrections can be applied to the inverted load magnitude using the relative error distribution curves obtained from the earlier analysis, see Figure 9. as examples. From the assumption of the uniform load distribution, each length segment of the load patch will have an equal contribution and correspond to a unique load magnitude offset error compared to the true load applied to the segment. Using the superposition principle discussed earlier, the relationship between the inverted patch load and the true patch load is simply

$$F_{true} = F_{inverted} / \frac{\int_a^b \xi(x) dx}{b-a}, \quad (10)$$

where $\xi(x)$ is the distribution of the relative errors along the horizontal direction (or local x-direction), a and b are the left and right end boundaries of the load patch. The method works for both the single-sided and double-sided instrumentation, but it is more favorable for the single-sided instrumentation because of its reduced error-canceling effect discussed earlier. For the discussion purpose, the analysis demonstrated below is based on the results obtained from the bottom-sided instrumentation, from the extended model with the bulb profile. The concept of the correction is illustrated in Figure 14..

Figure 14. The illustration of the patch load magnitude correction method.

5.2.2. Determination of the load patch parameter

Equation 9 proposed by Böhm et al. [10] can be used to determine the vertical position of the load center. The method has good reliability because it is derived directly from the basis of the classic beam theory. Load height is a parameter that can be challenging to obtain based on the shear strains only obtained at the gauges positioned at the top and bottom of the frame. Installing a dozen gauges along a single frame can theoretically work according to studies conducted previously [14], but the associated cost and

preparation time can make this approach less practical. As the first-year ice induced load is considered line-like with a relatively thin design ice load height, which has a maximum of 35 cm for the ice class IA Super as per FSICR [2], and the variation of the $\xi(x)$ along the vertical direction is relatively small, it is anticipated that the $\xi(x)$ obtained at the vertical position of the load center can provide a sufficient description to the distribution of the relative error. Now, the focus is to find the horizontal load position of the load center and the load length.

The relationship between the load length and the standard deviation, σ , of all the entries within F (See Equation 2) is found to be reciprocal by Böhm et al. [10]. The explanation behind this phenomenon is, the difference in the resultant ice load experienced by each frame, f_n , increases as the load length reduces, because the load redistribution becomes more limited compared to a longer load patch. However, Böhm et al. only derived the relationship between the load length and σ from a load patch that starts growing at the grillage center. To ensure that the relationship is transferable to the other part of the instrumentation region, a comprehensive analysis of the distribution of σ is again provided in this study. The load height is maintained to be 28 cm or 7 elements, and the load length varies from 24 cm to 200 cm. The calculations are provided for the load patches centered at each applicable mesh element within the trimmed model, similar to the approach taken under Section 5.1..

From the mappings provided in the Appendix, it is observed that the distribution of σ is highly uniform for longer patches that extend more than one-frame spacing, except near the upper boundary of the trimmed region, where the load patches extend beyond the effective measurement region. For shorter load patches, a non-uniform distribution is observed along the upper and lower 1/3 of the six frames beyond the grillage center, but the distribution is comparable at the center. Therefore, the method should provide a consistent relationship between the load length and σ as long as the vertical location of the load is near the center. A clear reciprocal trend is obtained from the calculations as illustrated in Figure 15.. Note that only the top part of the trimmed region is kept in the presented mappings due to symmetry.

To estimate the horizontal position of the load center, a method of calculating the centroid of all the force entries within F is proposed. The mathematical description is

$$C_{horizontal} = \frac{\sum f_n d_n}{F}, \quad (11)$$

and d_n is the horizontal position of the frame from which the force entry f_n is obtained.

To verify the reliability of the method, mappings are again provided in the Appendix for the absolute difference between the true load patch center and the estimated center, similar to the σ mappings discussed earlier. When the load length is short, estimations are considered reasonable within the first and sixth frames, with the maximum error of about 3 elements (12 cm) found between the fifth and sixth frames. However, the estimations beyond the first and sixth frames are close to the horizontal locations of the two frames, because in those cases f_1 and f_6 are the most dominant entries within F . This introduces a challenge when determining the horizontal load center. For example, the estimation of a narrow load centered horizontally between the sixth frame and the webframe can yield a result similar to the one that is between the fifth and sixth frames. To filter out the loads that are centered beyond the first and sixth frames, one possible way is to inspect the sign of the load entries, f_2 and f_5 , that are adjacent to f_1 and f_6 , in the situation when the predominant load is carried by either one of the latter two entries. The minus signs indicate that the load transferred to the second and sixth frames is causing a pulling effect, which only occurs when the centroid of the load is acting outside the frames and causing rotation to the plating within the first and second frames, or the fifth and sixth frames. This method is limited to a short uniform load patch when the structure deformation is linear-elastic.

This method works in theory. More work needs to be completed to investigate the applicability of the method to structures with different geometries. The simplified assumptions applied in this study can also challenge the method in reality. For instance, the distribution of the ice load is never uniform, and the ice load can occur at various locations at the same time within a grillage panel. If the confidence in the estimated load patch parameters is low, the method can potentially introduce additional uncertainty to the inverted ice load magnitude. The sensitivity to the measurement noise is another topic that needs further study. Techniques such as machine learning might be able to provide an opportunity for a novel solution.

Figure 15. The relationship between the averaged σ and the load length.

6. Conclusion

This paper analyzes the ICM-based ice load measurement uncertainties as a continuation of the previous research. As deriving ICMs from the FE analysis is an important part of the load inversion, studies on the influence of the gauge locations and boundary conditions are first conducted on a trimmed grillage model, and the model with a more extended geometry. Results show that the position of the gauge pairs along the neutral axis of the frame does not cause a visible impact on the outcome of the load inversion, but shifting the gauge pair location outward to a reasonable extent can be beneficial, as it increases the effective computation area. Although the overall impact between the trimmed and extended models seems to be small, the selection of boundary conditions becomes much less sensitive when the extended model is used. This conclusion might change if a different grillage structure is analyzed instead, but might lead to a more efficient numerical modeling practice to retrieve ICMs.

Using the extended model, both the global and local effects of the asymmetrical frame profile are studied. The global effect of the asymmetrical frame profile is associated with losing the symmetry of the grillage structure, when the structure is simple. It is shown that the face on which the strain gauges are installed can affect the accuracy of the inverted load. Although the single-sided instrumentation on the bottom face (the face opposite to the flange extrusion) provides comparable results to the double-sided instrumentation, the latter option might still be preferable given its better error-canceling effect. The local effect is relevant to whether the ICMs are obtained from pushing or pulling, which causes the frame to deform differently. The results obtained from the single-sided instrumentation are most prone to this phenomenon and may further amplify the uncertainties of the inverted load. From the analysis of the frame cutout, it is recommended that the gauge position be chosen wisely to minimize the error associated with estimating the vertical load center.

To reduce the load magnitude uncertainty, previous calculations associated with load patches of increasing length are repeated. In contrast to the increasing uncertainty as the load length increases, the analysis provided in this study indicates an opposite trend. Besides the capability of reducing the computational effort and making the structured uncertainty analysis possible for any load shapes and distributions, the superposition principle proposed in this paper can theoretically be used for the reduction of the load magnitude uncertainties. The applicability of the method is left for future studies.

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A Appendix

Figure A.1 The standard deviation of f_n (top) and the absolute difference between the estimated horizontal load center (bottom), of the load patches with 8 cm length and 28 cm height. The horizontal and vertical axes indicate the mesh element counts along the local x and y-axis.

Figure A.2 The standard deviation of f_n (top) and the absolute difference between the estimated horizontal load center (bottom), of the load patches with 40 cm length and 28 cm height. The horizontal and vertical axes indicate the mesh element counts along the local x and y-axis.

Figure A.3 The standard deviation of f_n (top) and the absolute difference between the estimated horizontal load center (bottom), of the load patches with 72 cm length and 28 cm height. The horizontal and vertical axes indicate the mesh element counts along the local x and y-axis.

Figure A.4 The standard deviation of f_n (top) and the absolute difference between the estimated horizontal load center (bottom), of the load patches with 104 cm length and 28 cm height. The horizontal and vertical axes indicate the mesh element counts along the local x and y-axis.

Figure A.5 The standard deviation of f_n (top) and the absolute difference between the estimated horizontal load center (bottom), of the load patches with 136 cm length and 28 cm height. The horizontal and vertical axes indicate the mesh element counts along the local x and y-axis.

Figure A.6 The standard deviation of f_n (top) and the absolute difference between the estimated horizontal load center (bottom), of the load patches with 168 cm length and 28 cm height. The horizontal and vertical axes indicate the mesh element counts along the local x and y-axis.

Figure A.7 The standard deviation of f_n (top) and the absolute difference between the estimated horizontal load center (bottom), of the load patches with 200 cm length and 28 cm height. The horizontal and vertical axes indicate the mesh element counts along the local x and y-axis.